

Exploring the etymology of “Horizon” and its ancient Egyptian connection.

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ΟΡΙΖΩΝ

Abstract

In this paper, I explore the etymology of the word "horizon" and its possible connection to the ancient Egyptian concept of the horizon. The word originates from the ancient Greek ορίζων (horizōn). The oldest evidence of the use of ορίζων in the meaning of the horizon dates back to medieval copies of the works of Aristotle. Interestingly, the ancient poets did not use the word ορίζων to refer to the horizon, but preferred to use "Oceanus." The word ορίζων also means "define" and is possibly a combination of ορί (hori) and ζων (zōn). ορί relates to "limit" and “mountain” but could also be linked to "rise," while ζων stems from the verb ζην (zēn), meaning "to live." Together, ορίζων could optionally mean "rise between the mountains to become (alive)."

Examining this concept, it becomes similar to the ancient Egyptian concept of the horizon. For the ancient Egyptians, the horizon was the "place of birth and death" of the celestial gods. Similarly, for the ancient Greeks, the gods were born from Oceanus, and in the meaning of horizon, it resembles the ancient Egyptian thought. The ancient Egyptian hieroglyph for the horizon is a (rising) sun between two hills. As the ancient Greeks had a close relationship with ancient Egyptian culture, there was likely significant cultural exchange between them. Although both languages differ greatly, particularly in terms of phonetics, it is possible that the ancient Egyptian concept of the horizon was adopted by the ancient Greeks when they composed the word ορίζων.

Introduction

There is something fascinating about the concept of the horizon. Before the introduction of the word "horizon," the horizon itself already existed from the beginning of mankind. The line that separates the sky from the earth was always present. So, when was there a need to define this "spherical line"? The word itself seems to originate from ancient Greece, but the concept was already known to the ancient Egyptians much earlier. For the ancient Egyptians, the concept of

the horizon took on a fundamental position in their religion quite early in their history. It is known that many ancient Greeks stayed for a period in Egypt and learned about the knowledge of the ancient Egyptian priests. Although the languages of ancient Greek and ancient Egyptian differ greatly, it is undeniable that during these visits, concepts were adopted. In this paper, the etymology of the word horizon and the possible origin of the concept from ancient Egypt are explored.

The earliest appearance of the word horizon with an undoubtedly meaning of the horizon dates back to Middle Age copies of manuscripts from ancient Greek writers. The oldest manuscripts include Homer’s “Odyssey” and “Iliad,” both dated around the 8th century BC. Since most of the texts are Middle Age copies, they were copied many times during the almost 2000 years and certainly contain translation errors, interpretations, and additions compared to the lost original works. For a study of the etymology of words, this is a challenging task when using these texts as source material. Luckily, some earlier Greek texts are available found on papyri and pottery, with the oldest (fragmented) texts dating around the 4th century BC. However, most of these texts are also copies. Actually, all original manuscripts from ancient Greek writers are lost; we fully depend on copies. And even if the medieval copyists were faithful to the original text, the ancient copyists were not at all (Turner 1968).

When looking at the oldest original ancient Egyptian texts, we find that they date back to around 2400 BC, not only a difference in time of more than 1500 years compared to the ancient Greek texts, but they are also first-hand original texts. The task was to find the Greek words for horizon in the available material, compare it with the ancient Egyptian texts, and find the possible connection. This appeared to be much more challenging due to the fact that no evidence for this connection seems to exist. A lot happened concerning the Greek language and the conceptual thinking in the period roughly between 800 - 200 BC, the period of the great poets and philosophers. Specifically, the period between 450 BC and 320 BC is of most interest, being the period of Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, and the conquest of Alexander the Great of the Middle East and Egypt took place.

Interesting is that the Greek word for horizon, ορίζων , contains $\zeta\omega\nu$, which is a form of the verb “to live.” If there is a link of the Greek word ορίζων with the Greek verb $\zeta\omega\nu$ “to live,” it would bring the relation with the ancient Egyptian language closer since the horizon for them was directly related to the aspect of “becoming alive.”

In this paper, I go through the currently known etymology and will discuss how the ancient Egyptians saw the horizon. Although the ancient Greek semantic of the word horizon is quite straightforward, there could be an origin that tells more, and the original concept may not be as straightforward as it seems. One of the oldest surviving Greek papyri, the Derveni papyrus, might be of help in justifying this.

Most Greek words in this paper I have used are written in lower case but the ancient Greek texts originally all were written in upper case since lower case characters developed much later in the medieval period.

Current etymology

According to various etymology dictionaries¹, the word "horizon" originates from the Greek word "ὀρίζων" (horizōn), without the letter “h”. The “h” was added in the 1600s to match the Latin form (Barnhart 1988). The word is derived from "ὅρις" (hori) meaning “boundary, limit” and the verb "ορίζω" (orizo) meaning “to define”. Literally translated it reads “defined by its boundary.” The original semantic of the horizon is the imaginable spherical line that bounds the sky and the earth (or ocean).

What are the oldest definitions given for the horizon? The oldest I could find is from Cicero (106 – 43 BC). He mentions that “horizon” originates from Greek, he writes:

“Cum enim illi orbis, qui caelum quasi medium dividunt et aspectum nostrum definiunt, qui a Graecis ὀρίζοντες nominantur, a nobis ‘finientes’ rectissime nominari possunt.” -Cicero, De Divinatione²

"For since those spheres, which divide the sky as if in the middle and define our view, which the Greeks call 'horizons,' can rightly be called 'limiting' by us," (trans. ChatGPT)

He states that the two spheres that divide the sky and the earth are called ὀρίζοντες (horizōntes) by the Greeks and called *finientes* (limiting) in Latin. The Latin word *finientes* comes from *finio* “to mark out boundaries” or “to divide”. The Latin word *definio* “to fix limits” but also “to give an exact description of”, is also related to *finio* (Glare 2012). In English we know it as “define”. Here we see a close relationship between “limit” and “define”. In later writings Seneca the Younger (4 BC- 65 AD) repeats Cicero:

“Hanc lineam, quae inter aperta et occulta est (id est hunc circulum), Graeci ὀρίζοντα vocant, nostri finitorem esse dixerunt, alii finientem.” - Seneca the Younger, Natural Questions³

"The Greeks call this line, which is between what is visible and what is hidden (that is, this circle), the "horizon", while our people have said that it is a "terminator", and others a "boundary-setter"." (trans. ChatGPT)

The Roman Manilius who lived in the first century, gives in a poetic style an extensive definition of the horizon:

“alterius fines si vis cognoscere gyri, circumfer facilis oculos vultumque per orbem. quidquid erit caelique imum terraeque supremum, qua coit ipse sibi nullo discrimine mundus redditque aut recipit fulgentia sidera ponto, praecingit tenui transversum limite mundum. haec quoque per totum volitabit linea caelum, nunc tractum ad medium vergens mundi tepentem orbem, nunc septem ad stellas nec mota sub astra; seu quocumque vagae tulerint vestigia plantae has modo terrarum nunc has gradientis in oras, semper erit novus et terris mutabitur arcus.

quippe ahud caelum ostendens aliudque relinquens dimidium teget et referet, varioque notabit fine et cum visu pariter sua fila movente. hic terrestris erit, quia terram amplectitur, orbis; et mundum plano praecingit limite gyrus atque a fine trahens titulum, memoratur orizon.” – Manilius, *Astronomica* ⁴

"If you want to know the boundaries of another circle, roll your eyes and face around the world. Whatever there is, whether the bottom of the sky or the top of the earth, where the world unites with itself without any distinction and the shining stars rise or set in the sea, it encircles the world with a thin boundary. This line will fly throughout the sky, now leaning toward the center and the lukewarm globe of the world, now at the seven stars and not moving under the stars. Whether your wandering feet take you to one shore or another, the arc will always be new and will change for the lands. Indeed, showing one sky and leaving another, it covers and brings back half, and it will mark its threads with a varied ending and moving with sight. This is the terrestrial circle, because it embraces the earth, and it surrounds the world with a flat boundary, drawing the title from the boundary, and is called the horizon." (trans. ChatGPT)

And Hyginus Mythographus (around 200 AD) writes:

"horizon appellatur is qui terminat ea quae perspicui aut non videri possunt" - Hyginus Mythographus ⁵

"The horizon is called that which terminates those things which can or cannot be seen." (trans. ChatGPT)

The Roman Macrobius, who lived during the fifth century AD, gives in his “Saturnalia” a definition:

"hinc est quod ubicumque terrarum steteris, videris tibi quandam caeli conclusionem videre, et hoc est quod horizontem veteres vocaverunt." – Macrobius, *Saturnalia* ⁶

"From this it is that wherever you may be standing on the earth, you see a certain limit of the sky, and this is what the ancients called the horizon." (trans. ChatGPT)

With the ancients he probably refers to the ancient Greek. I noticed that all Latin words containing "zon" are adopted from the Greek ζών, for instance *zona* (zone) comes from Greek ζώνη⁷.

A resource I find helpful for approaching the study of the etymology of ancient Greek words is a volume of collected papers called "Ancient and Medieval Greek Etymology," edited by Arnaud Zucker and Claire Le Feuvre, and published in 2021. The authors advocate for a practical approach that takes into consideration the cultural interpretations of the time instead of a more theoretical approach. They state that "Ancient Greek etymology is about finding the motivation of words, be it obvious or hidden" and "the meaning is more important than the form or phonetic material."

It's also worth keeping in mind that the ancient Egyptian script and the ancient Middle Eastern cuneiform script were not deciphered until the 19th century. This lack of knowledge about the ancient Egyptian language must have influenced translators and etymologists to attribute the origin of words to Greek and Latin. It's also important to consider that the ancient

Egyptians, Greeks, and Romans shared knowledge for centuries, during which words and concepts were shared.

The search for horizon

In Greek language the noun " ορίζων" (orizon) has the following different forms (declensions):

Singular:

Ο ορίζων (O orizōn) - the horizon

Τον ορίζοντα (Ton orizōnta) - the horizon (accusative case)

Plural:

Οι ορίζοντες (Oi orizōntes) - the horizons

Τους ορίζοντες (Tous orizōntas) - the horizons (accusative case)

These forms have been used for my initial research.

Oldest texts

When did the word "horizon" first appear and what evidence is available to support this? My research started with ancient Greek and Latin texts, such as those by Homer, Plato, Aristotle, Cicero, among others. Two sources I found to be the most useful and reliable were the Digital Loeb Classical Library⁸ (LCL) and Papyri.info⁹. The LCL provides access to hundreds of classical works in their original Greek or Latin text with the English translation, while Papyri.info provides access to ancient texts found on papyrus or other materials such as pottery. Both have a search engine that allows for searching specific words, which saves time in research. Papyri.info even provides links to images of the original texts taken from the material.

Although the LCL also gives you the English translation with the original text in Greek or Latin, I found that the word "horizon" is often mentioned in English translations, but when looking at the corresponding Greek text, the word ορίζων or a similar form is not present. The original Greek text may describe something that can be interpreted as a horizon, but when researching etymology, it is important to have a translation that is as close as possible to the original meaning. If these translation interpretations occur even in our recent time how would it be for the many copies and translations made after the first original manuscripts were created over 2500 years ago.

The oldest text with the meaning of the horizon that I could find dates from late medieval copies of Aristotle and later authors. Unfortunately, evidence for the origin of the word horizon on papyri I could not find. Table [A] shows an overview of search results of the Greek words for horizon in the meaning of “the horizon”.

Table A.

Word	Source LCL (from oldest to latest)
ορίζων	Aristotle (On the Cosmos, LCL400, p358) and (On the heavens, LCL338, p252); Seneca The Younger (Natural Questions, LCL457, p110);

	Plutarch (Moralia, Isis and Osiris, LCL306, p106); Agathias Scholasticus (The Greek Anthology 4, LCL 67, Pages 190-191)
ορίζοντα	Aristotle (Meteorologica, LCL397, p200); Theophrastus (317-BC) (philosopher); Strabo (Geographica, LCL49 p10); (Euphorion (Poetic Fragments, LCL508, p402);) Seneca the Younger (Natural Questions, LCL457, p110); Ptolemy (Tetrabiblos, LCL435, 6 occurrences); Sextus Empiricus; Galen (129-216 AD) (doctor and philosopher); Procopius (500-565 AD) (scholar and historian).
ορίζοντας	Strabo (Geography, LCL49, p44); Ammianus Marcellinus (History, LCL300, p446)
ορίζοντος	Aristotle (Meteorologica, LCL 397, 9 occurrences); Polybius (The histories, LCL 137, p444) Diodorus Siculus (The Library of History, LCL303, p140); Strabo (Geography, LCL49, 6 occurrences); Plutarch (Moralia. The obsolence of Oracles, LCL306, p356) and (Moralia. The Roman Questions, LCL305, p130) and (Moralia. Concerning the Face Which Appears in the Orb of the Moon, LCL406, p106); Ptolemy (Tetrabiblos, LCL435, 10 occurrences)
ορίζοντων	Strabo (Geography, LCL 49, p44-45)
ορίζοντες	Aristotle (Generation of animals, LCL 366, Pages 380-381); Cicero (De Divinatione, LCL 154, Pages 474-475); Ammianus Marcellinus (History, LCL 300, Pages 446-447); Dionysius of Halicarnassus (LCL465, The Ancient Orators 5. Thucydides)

Above result shows that the earliest use of the word ορίζων in the meaning of the horizon as separator between sky and earth, starts with Aristotle.

Because all these writings are copies dating from the Middle Ages it is not clear if the copyists literally copied the word horizon or exchanged horizon with text the copyist interpreted as horizon. It is however not surprising that it starts with Aristotle since he is the “inventor” of the empirical scientific approach. This new way of thinking required new concepts with corresponding words.

Next step was to search if the word exists on papyri dating before the Middle Ages. The choice in the beginning was to only use those texts that without doubt refer to the word horizon or also accept the translation given by the experts. Unfortunately I have not found any papyrus with a word for the horizon.

Ocean as horizon

In some texts I found that “Oceanus” sometimes could implicitly refer to “Horizon.” Aratus (230 BC) uses in his “Phaenomena” Ocean for horizon (Mair 1921). That Ὠκεανός (Ocean) is the poetic name for ὀρίζοντα is mentioned in a text from Euphorion (275 BC):

“οἱ δὲ ποιηταὶ Ὠκεανὸν αὐτὸν (sc. τὸν ὀρίζοντα) καλοῦσιν.” – Euphorion, Poetic Fragments¹⁰

"But the poets call him (i.e., the horizon) Ocean." (trans. ChatGPT)

Strabo (60 BC- 24 AD) mentions:

“τον αρκτικον δηλοι δια δε του ωκεανου τον οριζοντα, εις ον και εξ ου τας δυσσεις και τας ανατολας πολει.” – Strabo, Geografia I¹¹

“and by oceanus he means the horizon into which he makes the stars to set and from which he makes them to rise.” (trans. Jones 1917)

In Homer’s Iliad we find the following text:

“Ἡέλιος μὲν ἔπειτα νέον προσέβαλλεν ἀρούρας,
ἔξ ἀκαλαρρείταιο βαθυρρόου Ὠκεανοῖο οὐρανὸν εἴσανιών” – Homer, Iliad¹²

“The sun was now just striking on the fields, as he rose from softly-gliding, deep-flowing Oceanus, and climbed the heavens.” (trans. Murray 1924)

Here we see that the word horizon would match but was not used. In many translations of Homer’s Iliad we find the word horizon but when checking with the Greek text it does not show the Greek word ὀρίζων or alike.

The poets and the era of rational enlightenment

Poets held a special position in ancient Greek literature. In poetry, language was less strict and more fluid, offering the poet the possibility to match their words and sentences to the poetic style. It was not uncommon to find word conjugations used in one poem only and nowhere else, simply to give the right rhythm or sound to the poem. The semantics of a poem were much richer than in "normal" literature. Poets focused on feelings, emotions, and impressions conveyed in the text, giving more freedom to interpretations. On the contrary, non-poets tended to use stricter wording and grammar. For them, the semantics should be indisputable and clear, with no double meanings.

We can see in table [A] that no poets are listed. The main form of Greek literature was poetic until around 430 BC (Karamanou 2016). The era of the great philosophers was also a time when traditional religious thought was still practiced. This religion originated from the ancients and came under pressure because of proto-scientific thinking. This emerging logical thinking

and questioning of ancient (religious) thought must have led to conflicts and dilemmas. "The period was one of rapid change and development in Greece, a kind of renaissance" (Balme & Lawall 2003).

There is evidence of this conflicting duality in the oldest surviving papyrus, the Derveni papyrus. "The overall intellectual horizon that is at work in the Derveni papyrus could well be that of a rational Enlightenment turned against the two main forms of religious obscurantism: ethics is to ritual what physics is to myth" (Laks 1994).

The other meaning(s) of ορίζων

The Greek word ορίζων (horizōn) can mean besides the horizon also “define” or “setting boundaries” and stems from the verb ορίζω (horizō) “to define” or “to separate.”¹³

To determine when the forms of the verb ορίζω appeared, I followed the same steps as above, using LCL as a source. Table [B] shows the results.

Table [B]:

Word	Oldest appearance	Source (LCL)
ορίζων	500 - 400 BC	Xenophon of Athens (Anabis, LCL 90); Thucydides (History of the Peloponnesian War, LCL108); Euripides (Dramatic Fragments, LCL504)
ορίζοντα	500 - 400 BC	Plato (Laws, LCL 192)
ορίζοντας		No result
ορίζοντος	300 – 200 BC	Polybius (The Histories, LCL 161)
ορίζοντων	400 – 300 BC	Aristotle (Parva Naturalia. On respiration, LCL 288)
ορίζοντες	500 – 400 BC	Isocrates (Discourses 4. Panegyricus, LCL 209); Thucydides (History of the Peloponnesian War, LCL 109)

And again on Papyri.info. Unfortunately many papyri are in a such terrible condition that it is difficult to read the text to confirm words. In table [C] the results are shown.

Table [C]:

Word	Date	Source
ορίζων	400-500 AD	Papyrus (SB18 13894: lease contract)
ορίζοντα		Not found
ορίζοντας	200-100 BC	Papyrus (P.Herc.114: Fragment of Epicurus’s De Natura)
ορίζοντων	200-100 BC	Papyrus (P.Herc.114: Fragment of Epicurus’s De Natura)
ορίζονταί	100-200 AD	Papyrus (TM62580: Fragment of Plato’s Theaetetus)
ορίζοντες		Not found

I did not find any Greek word in Homer's texts that could be related to conjugations of the verb "ορίζων." This could imply that the verb "ορίζω" did not exist yet. The results show that the verb "ορίζω" exists in the oldest non-poetic manuscripts and predates the noun ορίζων in the

meaning of "horizon." Additionally, no poets appear among those earliest sources, which could imply that the verbs “to define” or “to limit” were not in favor in poetry despite their creativity in using words.

A composed word

Many Greek words are a combination of pre-existing words, and analyzing their components can lead to a better understanding of their semantic origin. The Greek word ζων (zon) means "life" and is part of ὀρίζων. Could the word for "horizon" be composed of ὀρί and ζων? The verb "to live" in ancient Greek is ζῆν (zēn), and ζων is the present active participle of the verb.

The prefix ορι

We saw that the Greek word for horizon comes from the verb ορίζων (to define), which in turn stems from ορος (oros)¹⁴. Besides “limit” ορος can also mean “mountain” which is interesting, as we discuss later, in ancient Egyptian, the hieroglyph for mountain can also mean horizon. The Greek word ορος has its root in Indo-European **h₃er-* “rise.”¹⁵ In this meaning a mountain is “risen land”.

The Latin prefix *ori-*, which stems from the Latin word *orior*, can mean “to appear above the horizon.”¹⁶ *Orior* is also associated with *Oriens* (rising – of the sun); *orientalis* (eastern); *originis* (existing at, the beginning); *Origo* (coming into being); *Orior* (To appear above the horizon, to rise, to begin, to come into existence, to be born, indicating place of origin); *Orios* (of the mountains, Greek ορειος).

The Latin word *orior* has its root in Proto-Indo-European **h₃r-i-* “to rise” but could also be from **h₃er-* which would be the same Indo-European root as the Greek word ορος.¹⁷ The Greek ορίζων (defining) has a close semantic with the Latin “*origo*” (coming into being) and “*originalis*” (existing at). After all when you define something do you not bring something into being? The prefix *Ori-* comes from the root ορος meaning “border, limit” or “mountain.” In Homer’s *Odyssey* ορος is used in the meaning of “mountain.”

The verb ζην

The word ζων can also mean life and is derived from the verb ζην (zen) which means “to live”. Adding ζω(v) to a word makes it a verb and “Basically ζω makes verbs out of anything” (Antilla 2000). A verb is in most cases linked to an activity which is connected to a noun. When things become active don’t they sort of become “alive”?

In ancient times, before the philosophical "revolution" which began in Greece around 700 BC, people believed that all objects were animated and had a living force. For humans, animals, and plants, this was obvious, but even air, stars, the sun, rivers, and so on were believed to be living gods or belonging to gods. For instance, priests performed rituals on a statue to bring it to life; it became animated. In ancient Egyptian tombs, you can find many pictures on the walls showing dangerous animals decapitated so that the animal could not come to life

in the afterlife. The pictures on the walls were thought to become animated. This belief was common in probably all ancient cultures. In those days an activity most of the times meant that something alive, mostly a god, was the cause of the action. In this sense an action was directly linked to expressing life.

We saw that the Greek word ορος (oros) means limit or boundary, and "to define" is closely related to it, as setting boundaries or limiting something is a way of defining it. In many Greek texts, ορος is translated as "terms" or "definitions." To turn it into a verb, the term ζων (zon) was added to create ορίζων (horizon).

The Derveni papyrus

One of the most interesting papyri is probably the Derveni papyrus, the oldest surviving Greek manuscript discovered that dates back to around 430 BC (Karamanou 2016). The text itself probably dates to an earlier time. The papyrus was named after the place it was found, Derveni, Greece. What makes it exciting is that it was written during a time when Plato and Aristotle were most likely still alive. The content of the papyrus is believed to be pre-Socratic (Laks, 1997). There are several reasons why this papyrus is relevant to this paper. It is the earliest evidence of Greek text where the word ορίζων could be written and it also provides parts of texts that demonstrate the dilemma of the belief in ancient Greek myth and the emergence of proto-scientific thinking, as discussed earlier in this paper.

Defining

The following text shows Column XIV as how it looks on the papyrus:

ΚΡΟΥΟΝΤΑ ΤΟΝ ΝΟΥΜ ΠΡΟΣ ΑΛΛΗΛΑ ΚΡΟΝΟΝ ΟΝΟΜΑΣΑΣ
ΜΕΓΑ ΡΕΞΑΙ ΦΗΣΙ ΤΟΝ ΟΥΡΑΝΟΝ· ΑΦ ΡΕΘΗΝΑΙ ΓΑΡ
ΤΗΜ ΒΑΣΙΛΕΙΑΝ ΑΥΤΟΓ. ΚΡΟΝΟΝ ΔΕ ΩΝΟΜΑΣΕΝ ΑΠΟ ΤΟΥ
Ε ΓΟΥ ΑΥΤΟΝ ΚΑΙ ΤΑΛΛΑ ΚΑΤΑ Τ ΟΓΟΝ.
ΟΝΤΩΝ ΓΑΡ ΑΠΑΝΤ ΝΩΝ
Σ ΩΣ ΟΡ Ν ΦΥΣΙΝ Ν
Σ. ΑΦΑΙΡ ΣΘΑΙ Δ' ΑΥ ΕΙΑΝ
ΜΕΝΩΝ Τ Ε ΝΤ ΝΤΑ.

(source Harvard University: Imouseion Project, <https://dp.chs.harvard.edu/index.php?col=14&ed=KPT>)

The text with lacunes filled:

“κρούοντα τὸν Νοῦμ πρὸς ἄλληλα 'Κρόνον' ὀνομάσας, 'μέγα ρέξαι' φησὶ τὸν Οὐρανόν· ἀφαιρεθῆναι γὰρ τῆμ βασιλείαν αὐτόγ. Κρόνον' δὲ ὀνόμασεν ἀπὸ τοῦ ἔργου αὐτὸν καὶ τὰλλα κατὰ τὸν αὐτὸν λόγον. τῶν ἐόντων γὰρ ἀπάντων οὐπω κρουομένων ὁ Νοῦς ὡς **ὀρίζων** φύσιν τὴν ἐπωνυμίαν ἔσχεν Οὐρανός. 'ἀφαιρεῖσθαι' δ' αὐτόμ φησὶ 'τῆμ βασιλείαν' κρουομένων τῶν ἐόντων,” – Derveni papyrus, column IV

“Because Mind was striking against each other, he named it Kronos and says that he did a great deed to Ouranos; for the latter was deprived of the kingship. He gave it the name Kronos after its action and the other (names) according to the same principle. For when all the eonta [were not yet being struck, Mind] as **determining** (orizein) the creation, [received the designation Ouranos (i.e. Determining Mind)]. And [he says] that it was deprived of its kingship when [the eonta] were being struck.” (trans. Kouremenos)

As you can see in the original text on the papyrus we do not read ΟΡΙΖΩΝ but only ΟΡ.....Ν. If the original would have contained ΟΡΙΖΩΝ then this is the oldest reference to this word. Unfortunately I could not find images taken from the original papyrus showing the text. Here ὀρίζω is translated in the meaning of “defined”.

Separating

In the meaning of separating the following is mentioned:

“και μοησηι το πρωτον χωρισθεντα διαστειναι διχ αλλιλον τα εοντα χωριζομενου γαρ του ηλιου και απολαμβανομενου εν μεσωι πιξας ισχει και τανωθε του ηλιου και τα κατωθεν εχομενον δε επος” – Derveni papyrus, column XV

“and cause the εοντα, once separated, stand apart from each other. For when the sun is separated and confined in the middle, it (sc. Mind) holds fast, having fixed them, both those above the sun and below.” (trans. Kouremenos)

Here we see that the words χωρισθεντα and χωριζομενου both are translated as “separated.” Both are derived from the verb χωρίζω “to separate, to distinguish”¹⁸, which lies close to the verb “ὀρίζω” for “to define” but can also mean “to separate”. The addition of the “χ” character to the root verb “ορίζω” was likely due to the influence of the noun “χώρα” (chōra), which means “space”, “place”, or “land”.

Implicit references to the horizon?

The usage of Greek words related to “define” started to appear in the earliest 5th century BC, which is not surprising because it was the period of the great philosophers. When reading the dialogues in Plato's works, we can see that they are all about defining. Socrates tried to separate what is true from what is false. The dialogues in Plato's works discussed subjects such as what is truth or what is good. Socrates approached these dialogues as if he were a midwife helping a pregnant woman give birth to a newborn. In this view, Socrates helped bring matters to light and see if they were viable”, when proved to be viable it is a truth or else false. It was like bringing something that was not yet visible to the visible world, the process of becoming and seeing if it would remain, becoming alive. In the times of the great philosophers, heavenly objects such as the sun and the stars became visible when rising on the horizon. The stars were still considered divine living beings or gods, as we can read in Plato's Cratylus¹⁹, for instance.

In a previous chapter we saw that Ocean could mean horizon. In the Derveni papyrus we can find some texts with Oceanus. For instance:

“Ρέα δ’ ὅτι πολλὰ καὶ πρὸς κίλα ζῶια ἔφυ ἐκρέυσαντα ἐξ αὐτῆς, Ρέα καὶ Ρεΐη κατὰ γλῶσσαν ἐκάστοις. Ἡρῆ δ’ ἐκλήθη ὅτι τοῦτο τὸ ἔπος παγωγὸν πεπόηται καὶ το μὲν πολλοῖς ἄδηλόν ἐστιν, τοῖς δὲ ὀρθῶς γινώσκουσιν εὐδηλον ὅτι “Ὠκεανός” ἐστιν ὁ ἀήρ, ἀήρ δὲ Ζεύς.
οὐκουν “ἐμήσατο” τὸν Ζῆνα ἕτερος Ζεύς, ἀλλ’ αὐτὸς αὐτῶι “σθένος μέγα”. οἱ δ’ οὐ γινώσκοντες τὸν Ὠκεανὸν ποταμὸν δοκοῦσιν εἶναι ὅτι “εὐρὺν ῥέοντά” – Derveni papyrus, columns XXII and XXIII²⁰

“Rhea because many of all kinds of living creatures were born from her; Rhea was named Hera because it is unclear to the many, but quite clear to those who have correct understanding, that “Oceanus” is the air and that air is Zeus. Therefore, it was not another Zeus who “contrived” Zeus, but the same one (contrived) for himself “great might”. But the ignorant ones think that Oceanus is a river, because he added “wideflowing.” (trans. Kouremenos)

It is somewhat surprising that Oceanus and Zeus are implicitly made equal by both being referred to as air. Did the author of the text intend air to be non-physical, as a sort of metaphor? If the poets did indeed mean the horizon by Oceanus, as we saw earlier, then the consequence is that Zeus is linked to the horizon. Zeus is also sometimes named Ζῆνα in this papyrus, which can also mean the imperative form of “to live.” Additionally, the text mentions that living creatures are born from Rhea, who is also personified with the earth. We now have the earth giving birth and Oceanus, who is linked with Zeus. If we move to the next column of the papyrus, we read:

“ἴσα ἐστὶν ἐκ τοῦ μέσου μετρούμενα· ὅσα δὲ μὴ κυκλοειδέα οὐχ οἷόν τε ἰσομελῆ εἶναι. δηλοῖ δὲ τόδε· “ἦ πολλοῖς φαίνει μερόπεσσι ἐπ’ ἀπείρονα γαῖαν”. τοῦτο τὸ ἔπος δόξειεν ἂν τις ἄλλως ἐρῆσθαι, ὅτι, ἦν ὑπερβάλλη, μᾶλλον τὰ ἐόντα φαίνεται ἢ πρὶν ὑπερβάλλειν. ὁ δὲ οὐ τοῦτο λέγει, φαίνειν αὐτήν· εἰ γὰρ τοῦτο ἔλεγε, οὐκ ἂν “πολλοῖς” ἔφη φαίνειν αὐτήν, ἀλλὰ “πᾶσιν” ἅμα τοῖς τε τὴν γῆν ἐργαζομένοις καὶ τοῖς ναυτιλλομένοις, ὅποτε χρὴ πλεῖν τούτοις τὴν ὥραν. εἰ γὰρ μὴ ἦν σελήνη, οὐκ ἂν ἐξηύρισκον οἱ ἄνθρωποι τὸν ἀριθμὸν οὔτε τῶν ὥρέων οὔτε τῶν ἀνέμων.” – Derveni papyrus, column XXIV

“Things are equal when they are measured from the center; but those that are not circular cannot be equal-membered. This makes it clear: She who shines for many mortals on the boundless earth. One might think that this verse has been said in different sense, namely that if it is at its utmost, the other eonta are more apparent than before it is at its utmost. But he does not mean this, that it shows; for if he had meant this, he would not have said that it shows for “many” but for “all”, both for those who travel the land and for those who go by sea, when they should sail, the right time. For if there were no moon, men would not have discovered the reckoning either of the seasons or of the winds.” (trans. Kouremenos)

This somewhat strange text seems to explain that the position on Earth determines what you see as the horizon. That's why it is for "many" and not "all." In this view, it is similar to what

the Romans Cicero, Seneca the Younger, and Manilius defined as the horizon. The last sentence seems odd since the moon has nothing to do with reckoning the seasons or the winds. In Plato's "Cratylus," we find a similarity in the following text related to the seasons where Socrates says that ὄρραι (seasons) have to be interpreted as dividers of winters and summers, "since they divide (ὀρίζουσι)." ²¹

“ΣΩ. Αἱ μὲν δὴ ὄρραι Ἀττικιστὶ ὡς τὸ παλαιὸν ῥητέον, εἶπερ βούλει τὸ εἰκὸς εἰδέναι· ὄρραι γάρ εἰσι διὰ τὸ ὀρίζειν χειμῶνάς τε καὶ θέρη καὶ πνεύματα καὶ τοὺς καρποὺς τοὺς ἐκ τῆς γῆς· ὀρίζουσαι δὲ δικαίως ἂν ὄρραι καλοῖντο. ἐνιαυτὸς δὲ καὶ ἔτος κινδυνεύει ἓν τι εἶναι. τὸ γὰρ τὰ φύομενα καὶ τὰ γιγνόμενα ἐν μέρει ἕκαστον προάγον εἰς φῶς καὶ αὐτὸ ἐν αὐτῷ ἐξετάζον, τοῦτο, ὡς περ ἐν τοῖς πρόσθεν τὸ τοῦ Διὸς ὄνομα δίχα διηρημένον οἱ μὲν Ζῆνα, οἱ δὲ Δία ἐκάλουν, οὕτω καὶ ἐνταῦθα οἱ μὲν ἐνιαυτόν, ὅτι ἐν αὐτῷ, οἱ δὲ ἔτος, ὅτι ἐτάζει· ὁ δὲ ὅλος λόγος ἐστὶν τὸ ἐν αὐτῷ ἐτάζον τοῦτο προσαγορεύεσθαι ἐν ὄν δίχα, ὥστε δύο ὀνόματα γεγονέναι, ἐνιαυτόν τε Ἐκαὶ ἔτος, ἐξ ἐνός λόγου.” – Plato, Cratylus²²

"For the name of Zeus, for example, is one which has been only imperfectly grasped by us and by all men; if we had fully apprehended it, we should have been able to give to Zeus, as we did just now to living and animate beings, some definition which would express the very nature of Zeus. As it is, in speaking of Zeus we divide the name into two parts; we call him sometimes Zeus, sometimes Dios; and the two names taken together express the entire nature of the god, for Zeus is the lord and king of all things which are or are to be animate, and Dios signifies the sky and the air, and everything which is clear and pervading." – Plato, Cratylus (trans. Benjamin Jowett)

In the same work of Plato²³ Socrates calls Zeus “the author of life (ζῆν)” and “through whom (Δία) all living creatures received the gift of life” (Fowler 1926). Two different names for Zeus but in translations always Zeus is used, which is not accurate. Should it not be “Giver of Life” and simply “God”?

In the Derveni papyrus we saw there is also a mentioning of Zeus, Hera, air and the marriage between Oceanus and Tethys. When Ocean is air, the marriage between air and earth is the horizon, it is the place where they “touch” each other. And the celestial objects (gods) rising on the horizon are their offspring.

In Homers’ Iliad we find:

“Τὴν δὲ δολοφρονέουσα προσήυδα πότνια Ἥρη· “δὸς νῦν μοι φιλότιτα καὶ ἕμερον, ᾧ τε σὺ πάντας δαμνᾷ ἀθανάτους ἠδὲ θνητοὺς ἀνθρώπους. εἶμι γὰρ ὀψομένη πολυφόρβου πείρατα γαίης, Ὠκεανόν τε, θεῶν γένεσιν, καὶ μητέρα Τηθύν,” – Homer, Iliad²⁴

“Then with crafty thought spoke to her queenly Hera: “Give me now love and desire, with which you subdue all immortals and mortal men. For I am going to visit the

limits of the all-nurturing earth, and Oceanus, from whom the gods are sprung, and mother Tethys, who lovingly nursed and cherished me in their halls when they had taken me from Rhea,” (trans. Murray)

Almost the same text is repeated a few pages further. Hera is going to visit the limits of the earth and Oceanus, which in the light of the earlier discussion, is similar to the horizon. Here *πείρατα* is translated as limits or ends.

Recap so far

The ancient people of Greece believed that the celestial objects were gods and born when they appeared on the horizon (Ocean). In that context, the horizon is more of a religious place. During the period of Greek scientific development, the time of philosophers, people abandoned the religious context, so the horizon as a place of divine birth became a neutral separator between objects to be able to define them.

So far, we have seen that evidence of the earliest use of the word "horizon" dates from medieval copies of works from Aristotle. Also, the word was not used by poets, giving it a "scientific" preference in usage. The Greek words stemming from the verb "ορίζω" meaning "to define" or "to separate," can be found on papyri dating back around 400 BC. In the medieval copies, these are found in the oldest works going back to the 5th century BC. Based on these findings, we can assume that the verb "to define" was not known before 500 BC. This is not surprising since the 5th century was the era of the great philosophers, a period in which defining of the world and its phenomena were under investigation.

When we consider the word "ορίζων" as a compound word built from the words "ορι" and "ζων," it opens a door that is interesting because it brings it to the concepts of "mountain" (ορος) and "life" (ζων), also ορι could refer to "rise."

The horizon can be found implicitly in Homer's myth, the Iliad. Here Oceanus, Hera, and Zeus play the main part. They represent the Ocean, the earth, the sky, and life. The heavenly bodies are gods and are born from Oceanus. Ορι, in the meaning of "rise," together with ζων, "life," gives the word "ορίζων" a possible meaning of "rise to live" or "becoming when rising." This alternative etymology of the horizon makes it "the place of becoming," which was a concept well-known in ancient Egypt.

The ancient Egyptian horizon

The horizon held a special meaning for ancient Egyptians. They believed it marked the places where gods were born and where they died. Celestial objects such as the sun and stars were considered to be gods. Every morning, the sun rises on the eastern horizon and on the evening sets in the western horizon. Similarly, at the night the stars rise on the eastern horizon and set on the western horizon. The appearance of these celestial objects on the horizon was believed to be the (re)birth of the gods, while their disappearance on the western horizon represented the death of the gods. The eastern horizon was considered the “place of becoming alive” or simply the “place of becoming”. Evidence of this belief dates back to the time of the pyramids,

although there are indications of a much earlier existence. Cheops's famous Great Pyramid was called “The Akhet of Cheops” or “Cheops' Horizon”, his “place of rebirth”. They even had an earth god named Aker who was the protector of the horizon, and he appeared in the beginning of Egypt’s history. This idea of becoming alive in the horizon took an important place in ancient Egypt's religion until the end of pharaonic rulership. Many names related to the horizon were given, such as “The Beautiful in the Horizon”, “The Excellent of the Horizon”, “The Horizon of the Sun Disk”, “The Great Horizon”, “The Horus-Horizon of the Falcon of the Golden Ones”, and many others, mostly referring to the sun god Re or Horus.

The oldest text with the concept of the horizon is from the Pyramid Texts dating around 2300 BC, but it continued to be in use. Hieroglyphs can have different meanings. They can be an ideogram (depicting a literal representation), a phonetic sign (representing how it sounds), or a determinative (determining the context of the text). The name for the horizon in ancient Egyptian was ʕḥt (akhet).²⁵ The following hieroglyphs were used for the Akhet:

 (ʕrt)²⁷
 = (ʕḥ)²⁸

Picture from pyramid text: , also translated as “One-Who-Lives-In-The-Horizon” or simply as “Horizon.”²⁹

Hieroglyph for Aker, God of Horizon:

 two lions joined, Determinative in ʕkr (aker) "Horizon (god)," also ideogram for same.³⁰

The hieroglyph (ʕḥt) meaning “place of becoming” or horizon.

Example taken from a Theban noble’s tomb (1500-1300 BC)³¹:

dwr·k *Rr* *wbn·f* *m* *ḏw* *sns·k* *sw* *ḥtp·f* *m* *ʕḥt*
 thou adore Re (when) he rises in the mountain, mayst thou worship him (when) he sets in the horizon,

Another example from a papyrus containing a hymn to the white crown of Upper Egypt:

 “when she rises in the eastern horizon”³²

We see that the hieroglyph is used both for the place of the rising and the setting of the sun. In the ancient Egyptian texts, the word horizon is mainly used in relation to the place of birth (rise) or death (set) of gods (celestial objects). In this aspect, the ancient Egyptian religious concept of the horizon differs from the concept conform Aristotle's. While for the ancient Egyptians, the eastern and western parts of the horizon were of most significance, for the ancient Greek followers of the scientific approach, it was just the virtual spherical line between the earth/sea and the sky. Since the ancient Egyptian concept of the horizon is related to birth, becoming (alive), and death, it might be linked to the ancient Greek concept by looking at the possible origins of the word ορίζων when considering it a compound word derived from ορί and ζων. In that case we leave the scientific thought and enter back to the myth zone.

The ancient Greek-Egyptian connection

Cultural exchange between the Minoans on Crete and ancient Egypt occurred through trading connections as early as 3500 BC. Due to the favorable conditions of ancient Egypt, they were able to develop into a highly advanced civilization. Surrounded by desert and sea, they were protected from invaders, and the yearly flooding of the Nile provided fertile land. Abundant food and good protection against enemies are important factors in developing a high cultural standard. Evidence of this high standard are the great pyramids of the Old Kingdom (c. 2700-2200 BC). In addition, in ancient Egypt, along with Mesopotamia, writing was invented. Writing gave a boost to cultural development in state affairs and religion. The level of culture in ancient Egypt was likely much higher compared to that of pre-Greece until around the time when Homer's works were written around 800 BC. During that period, the proto-philosophy of the ancient Greeks began to develop, highly influenced by cultures such as ancient Egypt and Babylonia. It is also the period when the Phoenician alphabet was adopted in Greece. The adoption of the alphabet and consequently the necessary conversion must have introduced new words. This period of language development, together with (proto-)philosophical thinking, gave the ancient Greek language a sort of fluidity. Additionally, there must have been reluctance from more conservative traditional thinkers, among probably the poets, to adopt this new form of language. Most likely, the traders and philosophers did embrace the change. Many Greek philosophers visited Egypt or even lived there for a longer period. In Egypt, they must have received scholarship from the priests about astronomy, mathematics, and religion. In Egypt, there were Greek colonies, such as Naucratis or Al Mina³³, where the exchange of knowledge took place for centuries. In Plato's Cratylus Socrates talks about the adoption of foreign words into the Greek language:

“ἐννοῶ γὰρ ὅτι πολλὰ οἱ Ἕλληνες ὀνόματα Ἐἰλλῶς τε καὶ οἱ ὑπὸ τοῖς βαρβάροις οἰκοῦντες παρὰ τῶν βαρβάρων εἰλήφασιν.” – Plato, Cratylus³⁴

“For I understand that the Greeks have many names, and likewise those who live under the rule of barbarians have received names from the barbarians.” (trans. ChatGPT)

In this part of the dialogue Socrates talks about foreign words that came into the Greek language what makes it difficult to trace the original meaning of words (Fowler 1926).

The founder of Western philosophy, Thales of Miletus, who lived around 600 BC, was an astronomer and mathematician. It is unknown if he ever visited Egypt because no documents about him have survived, but he could have. He is said to be the first to question mythology and explain natural phenomena using hypotheses and a naturalistic view, marking a new way of thinking that distances itself from mythical and magical thought. Ancient Egypt and Babylonia were much more advanced than Greece in the areas of astronomy and mathematics at the time of Thales. Therefore, it is most likely that his knowledge was rooted in the knowledge of these foreign countries.

Pythagoras (c. 570-500 BC) is said to have studied in Egypt, while Plato (428-348 BC) may have visited Egypt. Eudoxus (408-355 BC) lived for some years in Egypt and had a special interest in Egyptian religion (Griffiths, 1965). After Alexander the Great conquered Egypt, many Greek philosophers visited or lived in Egypt, marking the beginning of the Hellenistic period in which the Greek language with its many dialects evolved into Koine Greek, a more simple and standardized form used also in the Bible’s New Testament.

Conclusion

The word "horizon" originates from ancient Greek οριζων, and it was most likely defined during the time of Aristotle (384-322 BC) because the oldest texts with the word in the meaning of the horizon are his. Also, he was the first to study logic and the scientific approach. The earliest evidence of the word in the meaning of the “horizon” dates from medieval copies, but the oldest evidence for the word horizon in the meaning of "to define" dates to around 400 BC. The word horizon is a composition of two other words, "ορι" and "ζων." The word "ζων" is related to the verb "to live," and the word "ορι" means "mountain" but could also stem from "to rise." Conjugations of the verb "zen" (to live) are already present in Homer's Iliad and Odyssey, but the oldest evidence also dates to around 400 BC.

During the innovative period of a more realistic proto-scientific thinking, it is not far-fetched to consider "to define" closely related to "to live." After all, when you define, you bring to life in an abstract way. Hints toward this thought can be found, for instance, in Plato's Cratylus. During the time of Plato, it was still a common belief that celestial objects, like the sun and the stars, were gods and were born from the Ocean. Several authors, including Euphorion (275 BC) and Strabo (60 BC - 24 AD), mention that the horizon is meant with the term "Ocean."

In the Derveni papyrus, we read about the marriage of the earth and the ocean, and from this marriage, the gods are born. In Plato's Cratylus, we find similar texts. This mythological subject could implicitly refer to what is later named the horizon. When looking at the ancient Egyptian concept of the horizon, we find that it took an important place in their religion. For them, it was the place of "becoming" or "death," the place where the (celestial) gods were born or where they died. The eastern horizon was the most important place since this was the place of birth of the gods. Evidence for this belief, this concept of the horizon, is found in the Pyramid Texts and dates back to 2300 BC, almost 2000 years before the introduction of the horizon in the Greek language. The ancient Egyptian hieroglyph for the horizon can be a sun rising

between two mountains. Without the sun in the glyph, it is an ideogram for mountain. Here we have the link between the Greek word ορος and the Egyptian hieroglyph.

The concept of the ancient Egyptian horizon was already well defined when the ancient Greeks defined their Greek word for horizon. In the period when this defining took place, the ancient Greek language was under development, and many of the Greeks responsible for this process visited Egypt and probably apprenticed with the priests. During this study, they almost certainly adopted ancient Egyptian concepts into the Greek language. Although there is no hard evidence of such adoption of the concept of the ancient Egyptian horizon into the ancient Greek language, it is plausible. If the word horizon has borrowed the semantic from the ancient Egyptians it is interesting to see whether there are more Greek words having their conceptual origins in the ancient Egyptian religion.

Bibliography

- Antilla, Raimo 2000, *Greek and Indo-European Etymology in Action. Proto-Indo-European *ag-*, John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Babbitt, Cole 1936 *Plutarch, Moralia, Volume V: Isis and Osiris. The E at Delphi. The Oracles at Delphi No Longer Given in Verse. The obsolescence of Oracles*. Loeb Classical Library 306. Cambridge MA: Harvard university Press, 1936. p45, p79, p107.
- Balme, Maurice & Lawall, Gilbert. *Athenaze: An introduction to ancient Greek: Book I*, 2nd edition. Oxford University Press 2003. p201
- Barnhart, Robert K. 1988, *The Barnhart Dictionary of Etymology*, The H.W. Wilson Company. “Horizon.”
- Fowler, Harold North 1926. *Cratylus. Parmenides. Greater Hippias. Lesser Hippias*. Loeb Classical Library 167. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press. P68
- Glare, P.G.W. 2012, *Oxford Latin Dictionary. 2nd edition*, Oxford University Press.
- Griffiths, J. Gwyn. *A translation from the Egyptian*. The Classical Quarterly, New Series, Vol. 15, No. 1 (May, 1965), Cambridge University Press 1965. pp. 75-78.
- Jones, Horace Leonard 1917, *Geography, Volume I: Books 1-2*. Loeb Classical Library 49. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Karamanou, Ioanna 2016, *The earliest known Greek papyrus. Proceedings of the 28th congress of papyrology Barcelona 2016*, Publicacions de l’Abadia de Montserrat: 93-96.
- Kouremenos, Theokritos & Parássoglou, George M. & Tsantsan, Kyriakos 2006. *The Derveni Papyrus*. Leo S. Olschki Editore.
- Laks, André 1997, *Between Religion and Philosophy, Phronesis, Vol. 42, No. 2 (1997)*, pp. 121-142 Brill.
- Mair A.W., Mair G.R. 1921, *Callimachus, Lycophron, Aratus. Hymns and Epigrams. Lycophron: Alexandra. Aratus: Phaenomena*. Loeb Classical Library 129. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Murray, A.T. 1925, *Iliad, Volume I: Books 1-12*. Revised by William F. Wyatt. Loeb Classical Library 170. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Turner, E.G. 1968, *Greek papyri, An Introduction*, Princeton University Press: 106-108.

Internet sources

<https://papyri.info>

<https://www.loebclassics.com>

<https://quod.lib.umich.edu/a/apis>

<https://www.trismegistos.org>

https://www.lexilogos.com/english/greek_ancient_dictionary.htm

<https://leserables.tripod.com/verbs/participles/activeparticiples.html>

<https://Etymonline.com>

References

- ¹ The Concise Oxford Dictionary of English Etymology, by Oxford University, 2002; The Merriam-Webster Dictionary, by Merriam-Webster, 2004; The Barnhart Dictionary of Etymology, by Robert K. Barnhart, 1988.
- ² Cicero. *On Old Age. On Friendship. On Divination*. Translated By W.A. Falconer. Loeb Classical Library 154. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1923. p474.
- ³ Seneca. *Natural Questions, Volume II: Books 4-7*. Translated by Thomas H. Corcoran. Loeb Classical Library 457. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1972. p110.
- ⁴ Manilius. *Astronomica*. Edited and translated by G.P. Goold. Loeb Classical Library 469. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1977. p56.
- ⁵ Oxford Latin Dictionary. 2nd edition. P.G.W. Glare. Oxford University Press. 2012. p882 “horizon.”
- ⁶ Ambrosii Theodosii Macrobiani Saturnalia, by Jacob Willis, 1994, p450. Sat.7. 14, 1-10.
- ⁷ Oxford Latin Dictionary. 2nd edition. P.G.W. Glare. Oxford University Press. 2012. p2343 “zona.”
- ⁸ <https://www.loebclassics.com>.
- ⁹ <https://papyri.info>.
- ¹⁰ Euphorion, by B.A. van Groningen, 1977, p235
- ¹¹ Strabo. *Geography, Volume I: Books 1-2*. Translated by Horace Leonard Jones. Loeb Classical Library 49. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1917 pages 10 & 45.
- ¹² Homer. *Iliad, Volume I: Books 1-12*. Translated by A.T. Murray. Revised by William F. Wyatt. Loeb Classical Library 170. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1924. p344.
- ¹³ Etymological Dictionary of Greek, by Beekes and van Beek, Vol. 2, 2010, p1109, “ὄρος”
- ¹⁴ Etymological Dictionary of Greek, by R.S.P. Beekes and L. van Beek, 2010.
- ¹⁵ Etymological Dictionary of Greek, by Beekes and van Beek, Vol. 2, 2010, p1109, “ὄρος.”
- ¹⁶ Oxford Latin Dictionary, 2nd edition, 2012 “Orior.”
- ¹⁷ Etymological Dictionary of Latin and the other Italic languages, by Michiel de Vaan, 2008, p435 “orior.”
- ¹⁸ The Cambridge Greek Lexicon, 2021, “χωρίζω”.
- ¹⁹ Plato. *Cratylus. Parmenides. Greater Hippias. Lesser Hippias*. Translated by Harold North Fowler. Loeb Classical Library 167. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1926. p88.

²⁰ Harvard University: Imouseion Project, <https://dp.chs.harvard.edu/index.php?col=23&ed=KPT>.

²¹ Plato. *Cratylus. Parmenides. Greater Hippias. Lesser Hippias*. Translated by Harold North Fowler. Loeb Classical Library 167. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1926. p94-95.

²² Plato. *Cratylus. Parmenides. Greater Hippias. Lesser Hippias*. Translated by Harold North Fowler. Loeb Classical Library 167. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1926. p94.

²³ Plato. *Cratylus. Parmenides. Greater Hippias. Lesser Hippias*. Translated by Harold North Fowler. Loeb Classical Library 167. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1926. p48.

²⁴ Homer. *Iliad, Volume II: Books 13-24*. Translated by A.T. Murray. Revised by William F. Wyatt. Loeb Classical Library 171. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1925. p80 and p88.

²⁵ Allen, James P., *The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid texts*. Society of Biblical Literature, 2005. *Akhet*.

²⁶ Piankoff, Alexandre. *The Pyramid of Unas*. 1968, plate 41-42, p62; Allen, James P., *The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid texts*, 2005, p32.

²⁷ Alexandre Piankoff, *The Pyramid of Unas*, 1968, plate 15, p30-31; Allen, James P., *The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid texts*. 2005, p43.

²⁸ Allen, James P., *A grammar of the ancient Egyptian pyramid texts, vol.1: Unis*. Eisenbrauns Inc. 2017. p216 .

²⁹ Piankoff, Alexandre. *The Pyramid of Unas*. 1968, p62.

³⁰ Allen, James P., *Middle Egyptian*, 2005, p.429.

³¹ Gardiner, sir Alan. *Egyptian Grammar – being an introduction to the study of hieroglyphs*. 1957. p70.

³² Gardiner, sir Alan. *Egyptian Grammar – being an introduction to the study of hieroglyphs*. 1957. p380-381.

³³ An introduction to ancient Greek: Book I, by Maurice Balme and Gilbert Lawall, 2003, p201.

³⁴ Plato. *Cratylus. Parmenides. Greater Hippias. Lesser Hippias*. Translated by Harold North Fowler. Loeb Classical Library 167. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1926. p92.